

Activity Type [understandable]	Activity Type [useful]	Activity Type [user would use it]
Agree	Agree	Agree
Agree	Agree	Agree
Agree	Agree	Neutral
Strongly Agree	Neutral	Disagree
Agree	Neutral	Agree
Neutral	Agree	Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree
Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Agree	Agree	Neutral
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree
Agree	Agree	Agree
Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree
Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree
Agree	Neutral	Disagree
Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Agree	Disagree	Neutral
Neutral	Disagree	Agree
Neutral	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Agree	Agree	Agree
Agree	Agree	Agree
Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree
Agree	Agree	Agree

Activity Location [understandable]	Activity Location [useful]	Activity Location [user would use it]
Disagree	Neutral	Disagree
Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Agree	Neutral	Disagree
Agree	Neutral	Agree
Neutral	Agree	Agree
Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree
Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Neutral	Neutral	Neutral
Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Neutral	Strongly Agree
Neutral	Agree	Neutral
Agree	Agree	Neutral
Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Agree	Agree	Agree
Neutral	Neutral	Strongly Disagree
Agree	Agree	Agree
Agree	Agree	Agree
Agree	Agree	Neutral
Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Neutral
Agree	Agree	Neutral

Written Tests [understandable]	Written Tests [useful]	Written Tests [user would use it]
Neutral	Strongly Agree	Agree
Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree
Agree	Neutral	Strongly Disagree
Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Agree	Agree	Agree
Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree
Agree	Neutral	Neutral
Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Neutral	Agree	Agree
Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Strongly Agree	Neutral	Disagree
Agree	Disagree	Disagree
Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree
Agree	Disagree	Disagree
Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Neutral	Neutral	Neutral
Agree	Agree	Disagree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Neutral
Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Neutral	Agree	Neutral
Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree

TDD Cycles [understandable]	TDD Cycles [useful]	TDD Cycles [user would use it]
Neutral	Agree	Neutral
Strongly Agree	Neutral	Neutral
Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral
Agree	Neutral	Disagree
Neutral	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Agree	Neutral	Disagree
Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree
Neutral	Neutral	Disagree
Agree	Agree	Agree
Agree	Agree	Neutral
Agree	Neutral	Neutral
Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Neutral	Disagree	Disagree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Neutral	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Agree	Disagree	Disagree
Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Neutral	Neutral	Neutral
Agree	Agree	Agree
Agree	Agree	Neutral
Agree	Agree	Neutral
Strongly Agree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Neutral	Agree	Neutral
Agree	Agree	Neutral

Global Statistics [understandable]	Global Statistics [useful]	Global Statistics [user would use it]
Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Agree	Neutral	Disagree
Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Agree	Neutral	Disagree
Agree	Agree	Agree
Strongly Agree	Neutral	Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Agree	Disagree	Disagree
Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Agree	Neutral	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Neutral	Disagree
Strongly Agree	Neutral	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Agree	Agree	Agree
Agree	Agree	Agree
Neutral	Neutral	Disagree
Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Neutral	Neutral	Neutral
Agree	Agree	Neutral
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Agree	Agree	Agree
Strongly Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Disagree	Disagree

Privacy Settings [understandable]	Privacy Settings [useful]	Privacy Settings [user would use it]	Closure [user would use it]
Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree
Neutral	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree
Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Disagree
Neutral	Neutral	Neutral	Agree
Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Neutral
Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Neutral
Agree	Disagree	Neutral	Strongly Agree
Agree	Agree	Neutral	Neutral
Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Neutral
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree
Agree	Neutral	Neutral	Agree
Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Agree	Disagree
Neutral	Agree	Agree	Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree
Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Neutral	Neutral	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree
Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Disagree
Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree
Neutral	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree